

Inorganic P-fractions in a waterlogged soil subjected to wetting and drying cycles in presence and absence of rock phosphate

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Abstract : Phosphorus (P) transformation in waterlogged soil is different from that of non-flooded situation. Drying-induced soil aeration and re-flooding periodically alters redox conditions and therefore stimulate redox-sensitive processes influencing P binding forms. The release of available P from indigenous rock phosphate under this situation is another area of study in the present investigation. Drying stimulated mineralization of organic P and increased reductant-soluble forms. Drying of soils furthermore reduced its P absorption affinity. Single drying at early stage and remoistening is enough to release reductant soluble P into available pool. However, maintenance of two drying phases and remoistening to its waterlogged situation is more effective in releasing inorganic P in soils. Addition of rock phosphate further accentuates the release pattern of inorganic P in soil particularly where soils were subjected to 2nd drying and remoistening phase. Results also pointed out that all fractions of inorganic P are closely correlated with fixation and release phenomena depending upon the drying and rewetting phases.

Keywords : Waterlogged soil, drying phases, inorganic P-fractions, rock phosphate.

Introduction

Phosphorus is one of the most important nutrients for crop production. It ranks next to nitrogen in terms of importance, but it occurs in most plants in lower quantities than other two major plant nutrients, namely N and K. P-deficiency leads to incomplete reproductive growth, hindrance in energy transformations in metabolic and physiological processes and ultimately lower yield in terms of quantity and quality.

The available phosphorus in Indian soils is generally not sufficient to meet the requirements of plants for better or higher yields. Among the P fertilizers, superphosphates (SP) are considered to be the best for a wide range of conditions and are manufactured by acidulation of high grade rock phosphates. Indian deposits of rock phosphates (RP) are mostly unsuitable for processing into SP owing to low P content and a high degree of impurities (CaCO₃, Fe, F etc.). Recently, deposits of high grade rock phosphate (33–35% P₂O₅) in Rajasthan and low grade rock phosphates (<23–25% P₂O₅) mainly in Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Rajasthan, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh and

Kerala are found. A lot of experiments had been conducted to assess the feasibility of RP for direct application to soil.

Acid soils generally exhibit poor crop yield due to low P content. This is because such soils contain large quantities of Al and Fe hydrous oxides which can adsorb P onto their surfaces. Thus, much of the added P is 'fixed' and is not available for crops. So, more P is to be applied (as fertilizers) to raise the concentrations of available soil P to an adequate level¹⁴.

Changes in P-availability during drying and re-flooding have been widely studied in agricultural sites and wet lands^{5,4,7,9}. Chang and Chu (1961) observed that under waterlogged condition, the added phosphate is mostly fixed as iron phosphate.

Keeping above information in view the present investigation was conducted to study the changes in different fractions of inorganic P in a waterlogged acid soil subjected to wetting and drying cycles in presence and absence of rock phosphate.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

(a) Electrical balance : Model No. PB 602-S (Monobloc inside), (b) Spectrophotometer : Spectrophotometer 104 (Systronics, Serial No. 1361), (c) Centrifuge (Remi, Serial No. R-23), (d) Digital pH meter Model No. 802 (Systronics), (e) Mechanical rotary shaker (MULTISPAN), (f) Electrical hot plate (CENSIA).

Materials :

(a) Soil : Composite soil sample (0–15 cm depth) was collected from Regional Research Farm (BCKV) (22°27'47"N 87°0'45"E), Jhargram, Paschim Medinipur (West Bengal) during the year 2014. (b) Water : Double distilled water was used for the experimentation purpose. (c) Filter paper : Whatman No. 1 filter paper. (d) Fertilizers : Rock phosphate (obtained from rock phosphate reserve of Mussoorie, Uttarakhand, India; contains 17.4% P₂O₅), supplied by West Bengal Mineral Development Corporation.

Reagents :

Ammonium molybdate [(NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O], HNO₃, ammonium metavanadate [NH₄VO₃], NH₄F, NH₄Cl, NaCl, H₂SO₄, Na-citrate, Na-dithionate.

Soil sample preparation and analysis :

The soil was air dried, powdered, passed through a 2 mm sieve. The experiment was conducted in controlled laboratory condition. Two kg air dried soils were taken in each plastic pot. As treatment material, rock phosphate at 180 kg ha⁻¹ was mixed thoroughly with the soil of respective pots where the effect of drying phase(s) was studied in presence of rock phosphate. Altogether 8 sets of treatments with 3 replications were adopted for the experiment. The treatments adopted for the experiment are as follows :

T₁ = Soils were maintained at waterlogged condition throughout the experimentation period up to 90th day of incubation.

T₂ = T₁ + Rock phosphate* at 180 kg ha⁻¹.

T₃ = Soils were maintained at waterlogged condition up to 30th day where a drying phase was given and then the soils were remoistened to its pre-dried waterlogged stage on 45th day and maintained up to 90th day of incubation.

T₄ = T₃ + Rock phosphate* at 180 kg ha⁻¹.

T₅ = Soils were maintained at waterlogged condition up to 60th day where a drying phase was given and then the soils were remoistened to its pre-dried waterlogged stage on 75th day and maintained up to 90th day of incubation.

T₆ = T₅ + Rock phosphate* at 180 kg ha⁻¹.

T₇ = Two drying phases, one at 30th day and another at 60th day of experiment, were given and after each drying phase soils were remoistened to its pre-dried waterlogged stage on 45th day and 75th day respectively and maintained up to 90th day of incubation.

T₈ = T₇ + Rock phosphate* at 180 kg ha⁻¹.

(*Dose of rock phosphate was selected considering the farmer's practice)

Soils were sampled on 0th, 30th, 45th, 60th, 75th and 90th day of incubation and analysed for inorganic P fractions (Available-P, Fe-P, Al-P, Ca-P, Saloid bound-P, Occluded P, Reductant-soluble P) following the method of Jackson (1973). Fe-P, Al-P, Ca-P and Saloid-P are added together and treated as active P in the present investigation.

All the data were statistically analyzed following methods meant for Randomized Block Design (RBD). Their mean effects were further subjected to Post-Hoc test to identify homogeneous means. The means were compared with value of Critical Difference (CD) at 5% level of significance (p = 0.05).

Results and discussion

Irrespective of treatments, available P increased with the period of incubation (Table 1). The effect of one or two cycle(s) of drying and remoistening to its waterlogged situation is more or less same with regard to accumulation of available P in the soil. However, close examination of the data revealed that higher amount of available P is accumulated in waterlogged soil subjected to two drying phases. Addition of rock phosphate increased available P content in soil. The increase in available P is due to mineralization of organic P which is accumulated in microbial cells, and release of this P when these cells rupture upon extreme drying or rapid reflooding⁴ or under anoxic condition¹⁰. Although changes in available P

Table 1. Changes in the amount (mg kg⁻¹) of Available P in soil treated with or without rock phosphate and maintained under waterlogged condition as well as subjected to one and/or two cycle(s) of wetting and drying

Treatments	Incubation period (days)						Mean
	0	30	45	60	75	90	
T ₁	16.91	19.43	21.24	22.92	25.44	26.42	22.06
T ₂	17.19	20.41	23.06	25.30	27.81	29.35	23.85
T ₃	17.19	19.71	18.31	24.88	28.23	29.63	22.99
T ₄	17.33	20.69	19.01	29.49	32.01	33.40	25.32
T ₅	16.77	19.29	21.52	23.34	20.83	30.75	22.08
T ₆	17.05	20.13	23.48	25.72	23.34	33.68	23.90
T ₇	17.05	19.57	18.17	24.60	21.66	32.85	22.32
T ₈	17.33	20.69	18.87	27.12	24.32	36.34	24.11
Mean	17.10	19.99	20.46	25.42	25.46	31.55	
SEm (±)	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	
CD (p = 0.05)	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.03	

under different treatments are of lower order but the effect of treatment is significant at all the stages of sampling.

Results of active P (Fe-P + Al-P + Ca-P + Saloid bound P) in relation to available P presented in Table 2. Results showed that maintenance of drying and rewetting phase under a waterlogged soil is effective in releasing active P in the available pool which can be taken up by the growing crops. The oxidation and reduction state of the Fe and Al due to wetting and drying changed the fixing pattern of P by these active components of soils^{1,8}. Treatments are significant in retaining and releasing active P in soil at every stage of sampling of the incubation

study. Furthermore, maintenance of a drying phase at 60th day released comparatively higher amount of active P (Fe-P + Al-P + Ca-P + Saloid bound P) over that of the soil subjected to a drying phase at 30th day of the incubation. This trend of results is observed because of fixation of recently available P of rock phosphate and release of the same under drying and remoistening situation¹⁸. It is noteworthy to mention that active P fractions are susceptible to release P in soil in absence of added rock phosphate system as well.

Irrespective of treatments, comparatively higher order of occluded P is recorded in the soil (Table 3). Presence of higher amount of occluded P is due to the nature of the

Table 2. Changes in the amount (mg kg⁻¹) of Active P (Fe-P + Al-P + Ca-P + Saloid bound P) in soil treated with or without rock phosphate and maintained under waterlogged condition as well as subjected to one and/or two cycle(s) of wetting and drying

Treatments	Incubation period (days)						Mean
	0	30	45	60	75	90	
T ₁	160.41	231.54	262.23	323.60	351.50	384.98	285.71
T ₂	170.17	270.60	292.92	351.50	396.13	426.82	318.02
T ₃	156.22	239.91	188.30	373.82	396.13	421.24	295.94
T ₄	171.57	283.15	220.38	401.71	440.77	468.67	331.04
T ₅	164.59	239.91	273.39	354.29	312.44	443.56	298.03
T ₆	172.96	273.39	301.29	386.37	337.55	468.67	323.37
T ₇	161.80	251.07	200.86	376.61	331.97	471.46	298.96
T ₈	170.17	284.55	224.57	419.85	365.45	518.88	330.58
Mean	165.99	259.27	245.49	373.47	366.49	450.53	
SEm (±)	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	
CD (p = 0.05)	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.06	

Table 3. Changes in the amount (mg kg^{-1}) of Occluded P in soil treated with or without rock phosphate and maintained under waterlogged condition as well as subjected to one and/or two cycle(s) of wetting and drying

Treatments	Incubation period (days)						Mean
	0	30	45	60	75	90	
T ₁	106.01	136.69	145.06	159.01	172.96	181.33	150.18
T ₂	108.80	150.64	161.80	175.75	186.91	195.28	163.20
T ₃	106.01	139.48	119.96	164.59	178.54	186.91	149.25
T ₄	111.59	153.43	133.90	184.12	192.49	206.44	163.66
T ₅	108.80	136.69	147.85	161.80	147.85	189.70	148.78
T ₆	111.59	156.22	164.59	181.33	164.59	212.02	165.06
T ₇	108.80	139.48	125.54	167.38	150.64	198.07	148.32
T ₈	108.80	156.22	136.69	186.91	170.17	217.59	162.73
Mean	108.80	146.11	141.92	172.61	170.52	198.42	
SEm (\pm)	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.05	
CD ($p = 0.05$)	0.16	0.22	0.25	0.17	0.23	0.16	

soil of Red and Lateritic origin which is dominated by Fe and Al oxides. Maintenance of a drying phase on 30th day under waterlogged situation rendered maximum release of occluded P in soil (Table 3). Results thus pointed out that single drying at early stage is enough in releasing occluded P in soil. This is perhaps due to formation of higher amount of hydrated oxides of iron under waterlogged situation which bound P in occluded form. The drying may have facilitated formation of a crystalline structure of amorphous Fe-hydroxides in a process known as mineral aging thereby reducing sorption capacity^{5,17,8}. Results are statistically significant with regard to treatments at every stage of sampling.

Comparatively higher amount of reductant soluble P is accumulated in waterlogged soil than any other inorganic fractions (Table 4). Mean value of the results in Table 4 further revealed that although the difference in reductant soluble P is only 23 mg kg^{-1} under different treatments but the value increased over time up to 90th day and goes up to 120 mg kg^{-1} . Results further showed that two cycles of wetting and drying led to shift in proportion of reductant soluble P in soil. The accumulation of P is more prominent in rock phosphate treated system. The increase in reductant soluble P was likely due to the oxidation of Fe^{II} and formation of Fe^{III} oxyhydroxides, which preferentially bind P¹¹. The Fe^{III} would be reduced to Fe^{II} again

Table 4. Changes in the amount (mg kg^{-1}) of Reductant soluble P in soil treated with or without rock phosphate and maintained under waterlogged condition as well as subjected to one and/or two cycle(s) of wetting and drying

Treatments	Incubation period (days)						Mean
	0	30	45	60	75	90	
T ₁	153.43	184.12	203.65	214.81	223.17	237.12	202.72
T ₂	156.22	200.86	225.96	239.91	253.86	262.23	223.17
T ₃	156.22	192.49	175.75	225.96	237.12	259.44	207.83
T ₄	156.22	203.65	186.91	256.65	273.39	284.55	226.89
T ₅	153.43	186.91	209.23	217.59	203.65	256.65	204.58
T ₆	159.01	200.86	231.54	245.49	225.96	281.76	224.10
T ₇	156.22	189.70	175.75	220.38	206.44	301.29	208.30
T ₈	159.01	206.44	186.91	251.07	220.38	318.02	223.64
Mean	156.22	195.63	199.46	233.98	230.50	275.13	
SEm (\pm)	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.02	
CD ($p = 0.05$)	0.13	0.19	0.21	0.18	0.15	0.07	

Table 5. Correlation co-efficient among different inorganic fractions of P in soil maintained under waterlogged condition

	S-P	Al-P	Fe-P	Red-P	Occl-P	Ca-P	Av-P	Active-P
S-P	1							
Al-P	0.700	1						
Fe-P	0.921 ^a	0.691	1					
Red-P	0.921 ^a	0.731 ^b	0.971 ^a	1				
Occl-P	0.910 ^a	0.588	0.956 ^a	0.967 ^a	1			
Ca-P	0.890 ^a	0.396	0.895 ^a	0.892 ^a	0.962 ^a	1		
Av-P	0.872 ^a	0.762 ^b	0.874 ^a	0.940 ^a	0.878 ^a	0.799 ^b	1	
Active-P	0.942	0.837 ^a	0.969 ^a	0.971 ^a	0.921 ^a	0.824 ^b	0.918 ^a	1

^aCorrelation is significant at the 0.01 level. ^bCorrelation is significant at the 0.05 level.

[S-P = Saloid bound P, Al-P = Aluminium P, Fe-P = Iron P, Red-P = Reductant soluble P, Occl-P = Occluded P, Ca-P = Calcium P, Av-P = Available P and Active P = (Al-P + Fe-P + Ca-P + S-P)].

due to waterlogging¹⁵ releasing bound P⁶. Addition of rock phosphate increased the release of reductant soluble P in waterlogged soil. The result is in agreement with earlier works².

Results of correlation (Table 5) co-efficient showed that Saloid bound P is highly correlated with all forms of inorganic P except Al-P and combined active P, whereas, Al-P is significantly correlated with active P. It is also interesting to note that Fe-P, reductant soluble P, occluded P forms are highly correlated with available and active P fractions of the soil. Results of correlation study (Table 5) revealed that all fractions of inorganic P are closely related with each other during the process of fixation and release of available P under waterlogged soil dominated by sesquioxide compounds¹². It is, therefore, clear from the correlation data that maintenance of wetting and drying cycles has a good impact on retention and release of available P which is controlled by other active components present in the soil system^{3,9}.

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